

History repeats itself

“The object of the present volume is to point out the effects and the advantages which arise from the use of tools and machines ;—to endeavour to classify their modes of action ;—and to trace both the causes and the consequences of applying machinery to supersede the skill and power of the human arm.”

- [Charles Babbage, On the Economy of Machinery and Manufactures \(1832\)](#)

A Dangerous Closed Loop

“ We find that indiscriminate use of model-generated content in training causes irreversible defects in the resulting models, in which tails [outliers] of the original content distribution disappear. We refer to this effect as ‘model collapse’ and show that it can occur in LLMs ...”

Shumailov, I., Shumaylov, Z., Zhao, Y. et al. AI models collapse when trained on recursively generated data. *Nature* 631, 755–759 (2024).

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07566-y>

An Open Registry of AI Applications in Research

Responsible, documented use of AI

This paper presents the concept of making the use of AI in the broad research context visible, transparent, and properly documented. There are many reasons for wanting to do so, on the one hand to address some of the legitimate concerns about the use of AI generally and in science specifically, and on the other to leverage the experience and efforts of others to make such use discoverable, reusable, and accessible.

In simple terms: making the use of AI FAIR

At the root of our concept is a persistent identifier for instances of AI use in the world of research that we refer to as AIID.

Summary	This paper presents the concept of making the use of AI in the broad research context visible, transparent, and properly documented.
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Part 1: Context

Introduction

There is little doubt that the widespread availability, increasing usability, and rapid refinement of generative AI models will have a significant and foundational impact on the way humans create, record, and use its collective cultural works - including our formal body of knowledge. By extension, the mechanisms of scientific research and its contribution to this corpus are also likely to change fundamentally over the next several years.

The application of AI raises many concerns, and most of them are justified in one way or another. In broad terms, these concerns are of two types: those that deal with **processes** and human capability to manage, describe, understand, and continue to execute these processes independently of AI, and those that pose a question mark about the **content** that is generated by such processes - whether it is accurate, of adequate quality, can be trusted, and are readily distinguishable from human-generated content.

It is unreasonable to expect that AI will not be used at all in research: it is already being applied with varying degrees of effectiveness, and there is significant upside potential to increase the productivity and quality of research through AI.

In this paper, we do not address the question of whether increasing use of AI is a positive or negative development: we are concerned with the **responsible use of artificial intelligence** in those cases where it is otherwise beneficial and legal to do so. This means that we need to consider how to enable responsible use in terms of both process and content.

One should recognise firstly that **reproducibility** is a cornerstone of the scientific method. Any process resulting in new data, information, or knowledge that is opaque and cannot be understood or reproduced by another scientist is, by definition, inadmissible.

Secondly, scientific data, information, and knowledge are founded on **quality assurance mechanisms** that range from instrument calibration and precision determination through statistical methods to identify outliers, biases, and anomalies, to mechanisms to test consistency and logic of experiment design, exposing the reasoning underpinning hypotheses testing, and peer review of new assertions of knowledge. While these quality assurance mechanisms are not without deficiencies, it is deeply entrenched in the research workflow, and the constant scrutiny throughout the workflow ensures a broadly trustworthy outcome.

Both these elements of the scientific method are under pressure should AI be used without due care. In this paper, we propose the introduction of infrastructure and tools to address a specific aspect of process: making it a **simple and universal best practice to indicate the use of AI**, even at very fine levels of granularity, and to **record enough information** to enable citation, the requisite scrutiny, and possibly reproduction by others.

Citing all instances of data, information, and knowledge derived by artificial means has an additional benefit in respect of content that, in our view, is of critical importance already and will become more so over time: the ability to **explicitly distinguish AI-derived content**¹, and depending on circumstances, exclude it or apply it differently when new content is generated.

After a given date, which is likely to be sometime in 2020, [content in the internet has become increasingly derived from artificial intelligence](#)² (the “[Generative AI Explosion](#)”). In essence, it signifies the dawn of a new cultural epoch on the same scale as and analogous to the revolutions triggered by the printing press, industrialisation, and the digital age - except that **it is happening much quicker**. This has, amongst other things, significant consequences for future training data: since any content created after that date cannot be reliably identified as AI-derived, it complicates the process of selection of such data, and could lead to irreversible model deterioration [4]. It stands to reason that for some applications, training data needs to be limited to human-created or at least human moderated content, and expressly exclude machine-generated content.

Persistent Identifiers for Artificial Intelligence Use in Research

The solution we propose in this paper hinges on the provision of persistent identifiers to reliably identify and annotate instances of AI use in research and related activities. To do so, one needs to describe the context and particulars of such use (model, training data, tuning and refinement, purpose of the application), and provide infrastructure for resolution of the persistent identifier, supplemented by search and discovery services.

Implementation of such a solution ideally needs to align with a number of design considerations:

- Avoid duplication of existing resources - for example inventories of models such as those maintained by [Hugging Face](#), [AI4EOSC](#) and [AI4EUROPE](#).
- Build on existing service infrastructure for the provisioning and management of persistent identifiers, such as B2HANDLE, DataCite and Software Heritage.
- Make it affordable to issue large numbers of persistent identifiers, given that there would likely in time be hundreds of millions, or even billions of use instances that need to be identified.
- Try to avoid development of a dedicated metadata schema, but rather build on an existing schema and rely on simple extensions to such a schema if possible.
- The identifier needs to be as compact as possible, since its use will in some cases significantly increase the volume of data storage if applied at fine granularity.

¹ There is, of course, the possibility to detect AI-generated content using AI - but it is unlikely to be precise enough to use in many circumstances related to research - explicit identification with context is the preferred route.

² Interestingly, for some lesser-used languages, AI-generated content already represents a major proportion of the online corpus in that language.

- Align with any [relevant legislation](#), for example such as being developed and implemented in the European Union.

We provisionally refer to this identifier as an **AiiD** ('aid'), “**Artificial Intelligence (persistent) IDentifier**’.

Benefits of AiiD

An AiiD provides the following benefits:

- It **records** an instance of AI use. It is likely that for at least some of the higher risk categories of AI application, the institution where the content originates will be required to record such instances. It will be good practice to record many categories of AI application even at lower risk.
- It makes the use of AI outputs in research products (papers, reports, semantic artefacts, datasets, code) **citable**.
- It allows **management** of AI use in research groups, organisations, and infrastructures.
- It simplifies **showcasing** the scope of use of models, training data, and related creative works.
- Through publication of the metadata associated with an AiiD, such use is **shared** and aligned with Open Science objectives, and encourages reuse and widening of application of resources.
- It enables fine-grained **annotation** of AI-generated content of any type.
- It supports improvement of **provenance, reproducibility, and scrutiny** of AI-derived outputs.

How Will AiiD be Used?

The following section describes the broad user expectations that the AiiD service must address.

Practitioners - Researchers

The service must allow implementers of AI and ML in a research context to describe and persist the description of the particular instance of AI application with an **AiiD**, and then use that persistent identifier to do the following:

1. Cite the instance of use in papers and in datasets;
2. Annotate records in datasets, content in web pages, passages in papers, and any other uses of AI with the view to distinguishing it from human-generated content;
3. Add tags to web content to identify elements generated by AI (might require extension of some web specifications, for example schema.org, to implement properly);

4. Compile a registry of the use of AI in a specific research context, for example within a research group or project.

Users of Content

The service must allow users of datasets, web content, and other resources in the web to identify instances of AI and ML use, specifically -

1. In well-behaved datasets and research-related content, by providing an **AIID** that resolves to the instance of code, training data, and other contextualising information
2. In web content that has been annotated as AI-derived, opening a plug-in that indicates AI-generated content in the resource to the end user via an **AIID**.
3. Finding detailed metadata about a specific use of AI or ML as the resolution target of an **AIID**.
4. Searching the catalogue (registry) or AI and ML applications to identify commonly used models, training data, or other important facets, and to understand the landscape of AI and ML application through dashboard and summary views.

Institutions

The service must enable institutions to do the following:

1. Easily define and maintain a registry of use of AI and ML in its published outputs, and to provide details of such use to interest parties.
2. Provide a simple way for creators of AI and ML content to reference and annotate such content.
3. Contribute to a culture of responsible use of AI and ML in the content that they share.
4. Potentially assist with future legal and regulatory compliance.

What Type of Content Should be Identifiable?

There are two main considerations that determine what type of content should be identifiable, and by extension, documented in sufficient detail to be understandable, reproducible, and verifiable.

The first consideration relates to risk, and it makes intuitive sense to require that applications that carry or impute more risk should be more transparently documented and described. This notion is aligned with [recently published EU legislation](#), and as such, documenting some uses of AI will become mandatory through national legislation in EU countries in the near future.

The second consideration relates to the type of content generated by AI. Clearly, the use of predictive text or small snippets of language translation does not require the same level of reproducibility or documentation as sets of data generated or synthesised by AI, or significant proportions of content in reports or articles that were generated by AI, or decision outcomes that were derived from AI processes.

The proposed AIID service does not prescribe when it should be used to cite, annotate, or record the use of AI, but the following section provides some guidance in respect of use cases that we consider in scope for its use. The specifics of AIID use should ideally be defined in an *institutional AI and ML policy*³.

These use cases fall into a number of broad categories, and details on each of these categories are provided elsewhere⁴.

General Application of AI

- **Methods:** hypothesis generation, experiment design, and research process or workflow recommendations - these elements would typically be documented in a section on methods or as a formal methodology, and as such, any content contributed by AI needs to be cited and described in enough detail to be understood and scrutinised by third parties.
- **Content Synthesis and Knowledge Discovery:** text mining results, synthesis of content from appraisal of available published materials⁵, landscape analyses, literature reviews, and similar types of content in reports and publications: the source of the content needs to be citable, and wherever possible, provenance should be clear. Generative models are relatively effective at recognising semantic patterns, and as a result, imputing relations between concepts that were missed or overlooked by humans. Moreover, it is likely that AI will be well placed to enable cross-disciplinary research, which traditionally has been hampered by the necessary specialisation of researchers: AI can serve as a generalist in this context, able to translate concepts and approaches between disciplines.
- **Code Generation:** this is not limited to research and development, and is one of the most effective ways in which generative AI is already being utilised in the community.
- **Automation and Simulation:** includes automation of experiments, data collection and processing, and the simulation of processes, chemical and biological reactions, physical constructs, and both physical and virtual systems. It also includes automation of tasks involving a

³ Example policy to be added to the website

⁴ Work in progress: to be added to the guidance section of the website.

⁵ Generative AI models are very efficient at synthesis of summaries of published materials, in the same way that any human expert could potentially synthesise such a summary almost from memory and without referral to specific sources. It presents a problem in respect of provenance when AI models are used, since most public models do not offer the sources of its input data, nor does it make sense to list potentially millions of input documents for a given output. The question of provenance in generative AI is a separate subject of study and discussion with no clear guidelines emerging yet.

measure of human adjudication and consideration, for example by determining the level of sensitivity of a dataset.

- **Translation and Natural Language Processing, Semantic Mapping:** These closely related applications of AI all take a set of semantics and translate it to another, and some of these applications were the first widespread benefits from the application of AI to filter through to the general user community.
- **Classification, Pattern and Entity Recognition:** especially useful for such cases where the body of input data to be processed is very large.
- **Decision Analysis, Predictive Analytics and Optimisation:** this ranges from forecasting and policy or decision selection to optimisation of designs, processes, value chains, services, and evaluating the optimality of decision impacts and outcomes.

Some disciplines have developed more rapidly than others, largely driven by imperatives of profit and/ or significant benefit. Examples are discussed below.

Materials, Drug Discovery and Biotechnology

- **Materials, Pharmaceuticals and Chemical Substances:** modelling the behaviour, characteristics, and applications of novel molecules.
- **Molecular Modeling and Simulation:** AI can model molecular structures and predict how they will behave in different conditions, aiding in the discovery of new drugs.
- **Protein Folding:** Projects like DeepMind's [AlphaFold](#) have shown how AI can predict protein structures, solving a decades-old problem in biology and leading to advances in drug development and disease understanding.
- **Genomics and Precision Medicine:** AI algorithms are used to analyse genetic data, helping to identify links between genes and diseases and enabling the development of personalised treatment plans.

Robotics and Autonomous Systems

- **Automation in R&D Laboratories:** AI-driven robotics are increasingly used to automate tasks like sample preparation, testing, and analysis, speeding up research cycles.
- **Autonomous Exploration:** In fields like space exploration and environmental research, AI systems control autonomous robots, drones, or underwater vehicles to collect data and conduct experiments in challenging or hazardous environments where human intervention is difficult.

AI in Scientific Computing

- **Quantum Computing:** AI is being integrated into quantum computing research, where machine learning algorithms are used to simulate and optimise quantum systems. This can accelerate advances in fields like cryptography, materials science, and chemistry.
- **High-Performance Computing (HPC):** AI is often combined with HPC systems to handle the vast computational demands of tasks like climate modelling, protein folding simulations, or large-scale data analysis in physics and cosmology.

AI-Assisted Creative Processes

- **Creative Problem Solving:** In design and innovation, AI is used to generate creative solutions to complex problems, whether in engineering, product design, or architecture.
- **Art and Scientific Visualisation:** AI tools can help researchers visualise data in new ways or generate artistic representations of complex scientific concepts, aiding in understanding and communication, and potentially revolutionise the field of science communication.

These considerations are included into a candidate vocabulary whereby the outputs (application) of AI can be categorised ([Annexure B](#)).

Risk

AI applications range from those that carry very little risk (e.g. small snippets of language translation) to those that carry very significant risk - either to individuals, to corporate entities, to nations and regions, the environment, and to humanity in general. The European Union has directly addressed this aspect of AI use in its framework legislation that was recently published, and we see no reason to deviate from this classification. It forms the basis of a vocabulary proposed in [Annexure B.5](#).

Part 2: Service and Product Design

AIID: An Open Repository for AI Use in Research

Service Architecture

Figure 1 proposes a service architecture for realisation of AIID. Specifically, one would like to reuse existing services such as DataCite, Software Heritage, and Zenodo to the maximum possible extent.

Figure 1: High-Level Service Architecture for AIID

In this architecture, a metadata record containing a minimum set of elements that adequately describe the the application of AI (model, training data, tuning and parameters, input, performance, end use, output) is encoded using a reference-based metadata schema (in other words, all of these elements are pointed to by reference - say via URIs or PIDs). There could potentially be hundreds of millions or billions of such instances, and for each of these, we will be using the B2HANDLE service to create a stable and persisted **instance record**. The main utility of such an instance record will be to reference content and output generated using AI at fine granularity.

The instance metadata record can be extended for citation and publication purposes by a schema that is directly derived from and mappable to the schema in use by DataCite and Zenodo. Should anyone wish to cite an instance of AI use formally, the instance record can be extended to become a **publication record**, and this record is published via DataCite.

The publication record is validated against controlled vocabularies and registries to ensure that the resulting catalogue information is as consistent and machine-actionable as possible, and that any external references to software, datasets, and other materials are long-lived.

Registration of an AIID and maximising longevity is, however, potentially more complex than submitting a metadata record to DataCite. If the situation arises where datasets, models, or other supplementary materials are not yet provided with a PID in their own right, the AIID service **must in time** seek to rectify this by assisting with background registration of these resources in repositories such as for example Software Heritage and/ or Zenodo, and by linking these PIDs to a DataCite record, which serves as a container for related PIDs describing that specific application of AI.

End users of the AIID service can implement their own machine-to-machine interfaces via an API similar to the DataCite Fabrica service, optionally developing user interfaces to assist with capturing of metadata. The AIID service will in any event provide a lightweight metadata capturing UI (for both instance and publication records) as a reference implementation, which can be adapted by end users to suit their needs.

Because of the graph-like nature of the metadata, we foresee a secondary cataloguing component in addition to the B2HANDLE/ DataCite collection ('AIID Graph') that leverages and builds on the extension metadata and links between models, training datasets, and applications. A primary catalogue application that utilises the graph is relatively simple to implement using scalable indexing and discovery software such as ElasticSearch. The primary catalogue component also provides the target for resolution of the AIID by way of a detailed metadata landing page, as well as content-negotiable, machine readable views of the code, datasets and metadata - as applicable and feasible.

Figure 2: High-Level Component Architecture for AIID

These components are shown in Figure 2. As indicated, some of the components are either already in operation or available, while some can be repurposed from current Horizon Europe projects⁶. Doing so strengthens the community supporting the codebase, and improves sustainability.

The pAID will be issued by DataCite on behalf of the owner/ manager of the metadata record, and hence conforms to the schema for Handles, DOIs, and DataCite-managed PIDs. It will be resolvable via multiple endpoints, including the [DONA Foundation](#) (Handles), [DOI Foundation](#), and [DataCite](#).

One has to provision for and pursue early adopters, of which there may be several⁷ - and assist these organisations or services with the seamless integration of AID resources into their environments.

Metadata Architecture

It is important to recognise that in addition to the metadata describing the instance of AI use, metadata can be defined for three distinct classes, and that the use of AI in any context requires a definition of all three:

- Models and their versions are obviously important. To some extent, models and their versions are already registered (for example in HuggingFace and [AI4EOSC](#), which is synchronised with HuggingFace), but these resources do not supply a PID for each model version, and not all models are inventoried by these services.
- For each model, one can utilise any of a number of training datasets. In practice, publicly available models are closely linked to a specific training data set, but in principle, it is possible to use the same training data with a different model, and vice versa.
- Combinations of the same model and training dataset can be applied differently in different contexts, with different tunings and refinements, for a wide variety of purposes, and with varying degrees of human moderation, if any.

Each combination of model, training data, and context in itself may require descriptive and classification properties, and this combined set represents the instance of AI use that we wish to reference reliably and persistently in the publication record.

Based on these considerations, and mindful of the intended reuse of the DataCite metadata schema [39], one has to recognise that the DataCite schema is extensible in three ways without adding new elements:

- By adding controlled vocabulary values for e.g. `relatedIdentifierType`, ...
 - Requires agreement and endorsement by DataCite Metadata WG

⁶ Specifically [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) and [RDA TIGER](#).

⁷ For example [AI4EUROPE](#), [AI4EOSC](#), [HuggingFace](#), and organisations assisting with software development for researchers.

- By adding related Identifiers that resolve to specific extension metadata schema (SWHID, or any other custom metadata)
- By adding special controlled vocabulary entries as extensions of the ‘Subject’ element

The last option is particularly attractive, since the DataCite schema is essentially extensible without limit through support for collections of subjects (keywords), each linked to a specific controlled vocabulary in separate sub-elements [40].

Applying these three mechanisms allows us to define a simple extension to DataCite Metadata, requiring no schema alterations, as indicated in Figure 3. Vocabulary extensions will be required to accommodate AI-specific terminology for populating subject values (keywords).

The specifics of these extensions are summarised below:

Figure 3: High-Level Metadata Schema for AIID

- Minimum (mandatory) DataCite metadata will allow registration of a DataCite DOI as the basis of the AIID, and enable citation. It also enables indexing by services that make use of the DataCite corpus, if required.

- The model can be described by linking to an external reference, by preference implementing good practices:
 - A PID ([SWHID](#)) issued by Software Heritage, utilising their minimum requirement for metadata. SWHID provides exact versioning of code and applications.
 - Alternatively, registering a URL to a git-based repository for the code, but this is not ideal, since versioning is not managed explicitly.
 - Failing that, a URL to the code or model in a different location, such as HuggingFace or a dedicated site - again, not ideal, since the exact version used for a specific application may not be explicitly indicated.
- The training data for the model is likewise described by a link to an external identifier, which by preference is a PID:
 - A link to a data repository object via a PID (for example a DataCite DOI). The majority of DataCite-linked repositories are adequately managed and should implement good version control, although this cannot be guaranteed as in the case of SWHID.
 - Alternatively, a copy of the training data can be registered in Zenodo⁸ - making it referenceable via DOI, and offering an acceptable practice in respect of version management.
 - Failing that, a URL to the code or dataset in a different location, such as a dedicated site - again, not ideal, since the exact version used for a specific application may not be explicitly indicated. Some datasets are also increasingly managed and versioned in git repositories.
- The model context, parameters and tuning measures need to be recorded, and for this, a set of dedicated vocabularies are proposed for some of these (Annexure B).
 - Field of Application: a broad-based vocabulary that will assist with reuse of the approach.
 - Type of Output: in combination with the above, an indication of the type of output can be used to assess and confirm the risk profile.
 - Risk Category: based provisionally on the schema developed by the EU in its legislative framework, an indication of the risk inherent in the application of the model in a particular context.

⁸ Zenodo is not specialised for data storage, and may impose size limitations. It is convenient for smaller text-based datasets.

- Performance Metrics: This can be standardised in respect of benchmarks and the score achieved in each of these
- Model Use: information about the platform on which the model was run, the typical input and output that was generated, and test or validation information can be included here.

The scope defined above serves as a minimum metadata set for the application of AI models in general research-related activity and the infrastructure that supports it. It is, of course, sometimes necessary to provide much more information about models, training data, and application context, but a balance has to be struck in respect of the need for parsimony - which will be hugely beneficial in recording the use of AI with high frequency - and the need for detail, which is important in cases of impactful or higher-risk applications.

With this in mind, we propose a simple mechanism for metadata extension that relies on standardised extension elements that are not included directly into metadata, but is made available as a file-based reference in metadata. Such files, if they are provided using a standardised schema and using standard semantics, have three advantages:

- Extension files are only referenced if the context requires it - many applications of AI will not require any additional metadata.
- It can be extended without placing any obligations on the identifier infrastructure, since the elements are configurable and rely only on a community consensus for its implementation.
- Such extension files can still be used to index the main corpus of metadata records, since it can be used for facet construction - either through inclusion of file content into the metadata graph, through inclusion of these files into facets in the metadata index, or through free-text indexing. The approach to be followed will most likely depend on specific circumstances and the number of records that make use of a specific extension.

Hyperparameters, as applicable to some model implementations, is a good example of such an extension, and a proposed JSON file format for linking hyperparameter information to a metadata record is discussed in more detail in Annexure A.2.

Catalogue and Indexing

Figure 4 shows our proposals in respect of catalogue composition and its indexing. Nominally, the DataCite metadata collection provides a starting point for such a catalogue, providing an inventory of all items in the collection, and providing links to external resources: metadata records in external repositories, and optional detailed metadata in external standardised files.

Incorporating the additional metadata from external resources can be done in two distinct ways:

- It can be processed into additional facet elements in the catalogue - which is a natural choice if the elements are usually present in the external resources. As an example, the authors and contributors listed as creators of the model software and training data will often be present, and can be added as additional facets for indexing the catalogue as a matter of course.
- Some resources will contain elements that are not shared by the majority of AIID instances, for example specialised software or model parameters, or metadata dealing with very specific characteristics of discipline-focused training data. Such elements are best contained in a graph-like dataset, and can be used for either free-text search, natural language search and discovery extensions, or for constructing index facets that are context-specific.

Figure 4: Mechanisms for Catalogue Indexing

Either way, in practice it may be simplest to harvest all external metadata and process this first into a graph database linked to the DataCite corpus, and then to decide based on each individual situation whether an additional facet, or an additional text-based indexing is added to the catalogue. This preferred mechanism is shown in red in Figure 4. This approach has the added benefit of including any annotations made by third parties into the index after some form of moderation.

As before, the components shown in Figure 4 are of three types: those that are already available as operational services, those that can be created from resources created by H-E funded projects, and those that have to be created for the purposes of AIID implementation.

Linking to Established Services

A critical aspect of the type of utility, guidance, and examples that will be required from AAID relates to ease of use, and this by implication involves support for integration of AAID into the resources where AI is applied.

We propose a two-fold strategy to accomplish this:

1. Provide browser-based annotation plug-in services that can be used to commit a (minimum) metadata entry to the AAID service from almost any web-based context, and as a result, obtain an AAID directly.
2. Provide API services that will allow external platforms where AI models are invoked to register an AAID on demand. This will be relatively simple for services in Europe aimed at the research community (AI4EOSC, AI4Europe), and might be very difficult for generalised services (OpenAI services, for example).

Initial focus should be on building adoption, via projects such as AI4EOSC.

Part 3: Governance and Business Models

In this section, we discuss some of the considerations in respect of governance and business models.

Governance

Governance of public services to the research community needs to consider the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#) (POSI), which addresses aspects of sustainability and openness.

We foresee community-based governance for four aspects of management of the AIID infrastructure:

- A **General Assembly** of all those that contribute formally to the funding of the service.
- General management, strategic, and service inputs can be obtained from a **Steering Group** composed of subscribers or members, depending on the business model, supplemented by co-opted representatives of the artificial intelligence services and research communities.
- There is a need for a permanent **Metadata Working Group** to consider improvements to the metadata schema and its supporting vocabularies. Once could consider establishment of an RDA Working Group with the assistance of the RDA TIGER project before the end of 2025 to kickstart the process of Metadata schema design and vocabulary confirmation.
- User inputs and experience, feedback, and requests for new features and services should be considered periodically by a **User Board**.

Governance Structures - Composition

Stakeholder Group	General Assembly	Steering Group	Metadata WG	User Board
Funding Contributors	One vote per organisation	Nominated and elected by General Assembly	Self-nomination from funding contributors	Self-nomination from funding contributors
Major AI and ML Services and Platforms	N/A	Non-voting, invited by Steering Group	Invitations by Metadata WG, self-nomination and confirmation by Metadata WG	Invitations by User Board, self-nomination and confirmation by User Board

AI and ML Researchers			Self-nomination and confirmation by Metadata WG	Self-nomination and confirmation by User Board
End Users		N/A		
EU Projects/ EOSC		Non-voting, invited by Steering Group	Invitations by Metadata WG	N/A
EU Legislation Experts				

The governance structures will likely function best as a combination of close stakeholders (those funding the service in one way or another), and participants from a wider stakeholder group - end users, service providers, and researchers in the field of AI and ML.

In the EU, projects that are funded to contribute to the shared AI infrastructure for EOSC, and commission experts in respect of legislation and regulation also present valuable potential participants in the governance structures.

Business Model

Considerations include:

- The business model needs to ensure that service can be provided 24/7 and is adequately funded to do so. Should DataCite provide the back-end infrastructure for such a service, basic metadata registration and PID resolution services will depend on their cost and recovery mechanisms, and needs to align with these.
- The AIID service requires additional infrastructure that does not form part of the core DataCite service (annotation, graph database, search and discovery). This may add significantly to the cost of service.
- In line with recommendations in POSI, revenue should support sustainable operations, but also provide some funding for innovation and growth.
- The AIID service may require tens of millions or even hundreds of millions of PIDs to be registered, and as a result, unit cost will likely have to fall steeply with volume to make the service affordable, while still meeting sustainability objectives.

It is also likely that the service needs to be stratified in terms of scope and cost of service to suit distinct modes of use, as indicated in the table below.

We propose the following client categories:

- **Casual Users:** users that need not be identified, and makes use of free services.
- **Identified Users:** users that need to be identifiable via some identity provider (Google, Edugain, ORCID, ...) in order to make annotations, save preferences, and configure elements of service.
- **Subscription Users:** These users require access to unlimited API services and can create AIIDs within a given volume limitation for a single suffix. Suitable for individual research projects, collaboration projects, and similar short-lived initiatives.
- **Institutional Users:** For users that require high volume and/ or long term use of the AIID services, unlimited suffixes, and unlimited user accounts.

Service Aspect	Casual Users	Identified Users	Subscription Users	Institutional
Resolve AIID	Free	Free	Included	Included
Search and discover				
Public API (read-only)				
Factory API access (read and write)	N/A	N/A	Yes	Yes
API rate limitations	N/A	Yes	No	No
Annotate web content	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes
Configure and save queries	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes
Configure dashboards	N/A	Yes	Yes	Yes
Configure annotation schema	N/A	N/A	Yes	Yes
Create suffixes	N/A	N/A	1	Unlimited
Number of accounts	N/A	1	5	Unlimited

Part 4: Roadmap

Implementation of the AIID service will require funding, as well as support from important role-players in the landscape. Development of a fully fledged product offering is not limited to technical aspects, but should also aim to establish aspects of sustainability (governance, revenue), and create collateral (support materials, documentation, guidelines and best practices).

Our roadmap proposes an implementation plan for the next three years.

Planning Element	2024 Q4	2025 Q1	2025 Q2	2025 Q3	2025 Q4	2026 Q1	2026 Q2	2026 Q3	2026 Q4	2027
Consortium Building										
Promoter Consortium	MOU Signed	Operational								
OSCARs/ Foundation Consortium	Consortium Establishment		Operational							
HE Consortium	Consortium Establishment		Operational							
Governance Mechanisms										
Metadata	Confirmation - DataCite Metadata Extensions		RDA AI Application Instance Metadata WG				Metadata WG Commencement			
Steering Group			Canvassing and Communication		Informal Inputs, possibly via RDA WG			Formal Steering Group Commencement		
General Assembly					Marketing to Existing DataCite Members			First GA Meeting		
Business Establishment										
Membership/ Business Model	Options, Feasibility, Proposal Development		Product and Service Development, Accounting Infrastructure				Operationalisation			
Income Stream	Promoter-Funded		Grant-Funded				Service Commencement			
Marketing and Communication										

Concept Development	White Paper	OSCARS Proposal	HE Proposal Foundation Proposals		Peer-Reviewed Paper
Collateral	Preliminary Support and Website Materials	Website and Support Materials Professionalisation, Helpdesk Establishment			Website and Support Channels Operational
Events			Launch Event RDA Plenary 25	Official Launch Preparation	Official Launch
Service Development					
DataCite Service	Prototype	Beta Release	Feedback Period	Operational Release v1	Feedback Operational Release v2
Search and Discovery	Prototype	Beta Release	Feedback Period	Operational Release v1	Feedback Operational Release v2
Website Development	Prototype	Beta Release	Feedback Period	Operational Release v1	Feedback Operational Release v2
Graph Database		Prototype	Beta Release	Feedback Period	Operational Release v1 Feedback Operational Release v2
Scaling	Ability to accommodate up to a 100,000 PIDs			Ability to accommodate up to a million PIDs	Beyond 1 million
Funding Sources					
OSCARS	Call	Outcome	Execution		
Horizon Europe		Call	Submission	Outcome	Execution
Foundations	Submission	Outcome	Execution		

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Annexure A: Metadata Schema

A.1 Metadata Scope

1. Standard Metadata:

- **Title:** A title and a description of the model, its training data, and its application
- **Creator and Contributors:** Information about the individuals or teams who developed and contributed to the application of AI in this context.
- **Publication:** Information about the date of publication (date of use) and the publisher
- **Usage and Access Rights:** Information on who can access and use the model, including any licensing and intellectual property considerations.

2. Model

- **Model Name and Version:**
 - i. **Model Name:** The name or identifier of the AI/ML model.
 - ii. **Model Version:** The version number or identifier of the specific model iteration.
- **Model Description:** A brief description of the model, including its purpose and any unique characteristics.
- **Model Code and Framework:**
 - i. **Model Code Repository:** URL or location where the model's code is stored (e.g., GitHub link).
 - ii. **Model PID:** If available, for example SWHID
 - 1. **PID Type**
 - iii. **Framework and Libraries:** The AI/ML frameworks (e.g., TensorFlow, PyTorch) and libraries used.

3. Training Data:

- **Training Data Name and Version:**
 - i. **Training Dataset Name**
 - ii. **Training Data Version:** The version of the dataset used for training.

- **Training Data Description:** Description of the dataset, including the source, content, and any preprocessing steps.
- **Training Data Resource:**
 - i. **Data Repository:** URL or location where the model's training dataset is stored (e.g., GitHub link, repository link).
 - ii. **Dataset PID:** If available, for example Zenodo DOI.

4. **Context:**

- **Field of Application:** The specific domain or field where the AI/ML model is applied (e.g., healthcare, finance, natural language processing - should refer to a controlled vocabulary).
- **Type of Output:** The nature of the output generated by the model (e.g., classification, regression, generative content).

5. **Performance Metrics:**

- Key metrics used to evaluate the model's performance (e.g., accuracy, F1 score, precision, recall).

6. **Training and Deployment Environment:**

- Details about the hardware and software environment used for training and deploying the model (e.g., cloud platform, on-premise, specific hardware).

Additional useful metadata elements, which can be encapsulated in a separate standardised file structure, might include:

- **Hyperparameters:** The hyperparameters used in the model training.
- **Training Duration:** The time taken to train the model.
- **Model Dependencies:** Dependencies or external resources required by the model.
- **Evaluation Data:** Details about the dataset used for model evaluation.
- **Ethical Considerations:** Any ethical considerations or bias mitigation strategies that were implemented.

These elements provide additional documentation on AI and ML models, facilitating their reuse, scrutiny, evaluation, and continuous improvement within the research ecosystem.

A.2 Hyperparameters

Hyperparameters are crucial in fine-tuning any model that relies on training data. The parameters are set before the training process and directly influence the model's learning process and performance. Not all AI and ML models require them, but subsets of the list below are common across many:

A.2.1 General Hyperparameters (applicable to most models)

- **Learning Rate (α):** Determines the step size during the optimisation process. A smaller learning rate can converge to the optimal solution more accurately but may take longer, while a larger learning rate speeds up training but risks overshooting the optimal solution.
- **Batch Size:** The number of training examples used in one iteration to update the model parameters. Smaller batch sizes provide a more accurate estimate of the gradient but increase computational cost, while larger batch sizes speed up training but may lead to less precise updates.
- **Number of Epochs:** The number of times the entire training dataset passes through the model. More epochs can lead to better training but might also cause overfitting, and eventually cause deterioration if the training data is updated recursively [\[4\]](#).
- **Regularisation Parameters (λ):** Include parameters such as L1 and L2 regularisation that penalise large coefficients to prevent overfitting.
- **Optimiser:** The algorithm used to minimise the loss function and update the model parameters. Examples include Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD), Adam, RMSprop, and Adagrad.

A.2.2 Hyperparameters for Neural Networks

- **Number of Layers:** The number of hidden layers in the network. More layers can capture complex patterns but increase the risk of overfitting and computational cost.
- **Number of Units per Layer:** The number of neurons in each hidden layer. More units allow the network to learn more complex representations but also increase the risk of overfitting.
- **Activation Function:** The function applied to each neuron's output to introduce non-linearity (e.g., ReLU, Sigmoid, Tanh). The choice of activation function can significantly affect the model's ability to learn complex patterns.
- **Dropout Rate:** A regularisation technique that involves randomly setting a fraction of input units to zero at each update during training. This helps prevent overfitting by ensuring the model doesn't rely too heavily on any single neuron.
- **Learning Rate Decay:** The rate at which the learning rate decreases over time.

- **Momentum:** Helps accelerate gradient vectors in the right directions, thus leading to faster convergence.

A.2.3 Hyperparameters for Other Models

A.2.3.1 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

- **Kernel Size:** The size of the filter applied in convolutional layers. Smaller kernels capture finer details, while larger kernels capture more general features.
- **Stride:** The step size by which the filter moves across the input. Larger strides reduce the spatial dimensions more quickly but may miss finer details.
- **Pooling Size:** The size of the pooling window used in pooling layers to reduce the spatial dimensions. Common pooling operations include max pooling and average pooling.

A.2.3.2 Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Variants (e.g., LSTM, GRU)

- **Sequence Length:** The length of input sequences processed by the model. Longer sequences capture more context but require more memory and computational power.
- **Hidden State Size:** The size of the hidden state in RNN cells. Larger hidden states can capture more information but also increase the model's complexity and risk of overfitting.

A.2.3.4 Decision Trees and Ensembles (e.g., Random Forest, Gradient Boosting)

- **Maximum Depth:** The maximum depth of the tree. Deeper trees can model more complex relationships but are more prone to overfitting.
- **Minimum Samples Split:** The minimum number of samples required to split an internal node. Higher values prevent the model from learning overly specific patterns.
- **Minimum Samples Leaf:** The minimum number of samples required to be at a leaf node. Higher values prevent the model from learning overly specific patterns.
- **Number of Estimators:** For ensemble methods, the number of trees in the forest (Random Forest) or the number of boosting stages (Gradient Boosting). More estimators typically improve performance but increase computational cost.

A.2.3.5 Support Vector Machines (SVM)

- **C (Regularization Parameter):** Controls the trade-off between achieving a low error on the training data and minimising the model complexity. A smaller value of C creates a wider margin at the cost of more classification errors.

- **Kernel:** The type of kernel function used to transform the data (e.g., linear, polynomial, radial basis function or RBF). The choice of kernel can significantly impact the model's performance.
- **Gamma:** For non-linear kernels such as RBF, gamma defines how far the influence of a single training example reaches. Low values mean 'far' and high values mean 'close'.

These hyperparameters need to be tuned to optimise model performance, often through methods like grid search, random search, or more sophisticated techniques such as Bayesian optimisation.

A.3 Metadata Description

The following section contains a proposal in respect of a metadata schema for AAID persistent identifiers.

A.3.1 Metadata Schema

This is work in progress

Source	Category	Element	Description	DataCite Element	Obligation	Cardinality	Vocabulary Source(s)
DataCite	Administrative	Identifier	Assigned by the system based on Zenodo, has to be unique by deposit	Identifier	Mandatory	1	AIID allocates a PID
DataCite	Administrative	Language	A controlled vocabulary value [7]	Language	Recommended	0..1	Language List
DataCite	Administrative	Date Available	In case of an embargo, else publication date	Date Available	Recommended	0..1	
DataCite	Citation	Title	A title for the use of AI in a specific content, provided by the depositor	Title	Mandatory	1	
DataCite	Citation	Subtitle	A subtitle provided by the depositor	Subtitle	Optional	0..1	
DataCite	Citation	Contributors	Name and function of authors and contributors to the instance of AI use	Contributors	Mandatory	1..n	ORCID

DataCite	Citation	Description	Some written context on the use of AI. Guidelines to be provided by AIID.	Description	Mandatory	1	
DataCite	Citation	Publisher	Institution - often the rights holder	Publisher	Mandatory	1	RoR Registry
DataCite	Citation	Publication Date	The date of publication of the resource	Publication Date	Mandatory	1	
DataCite	Citation	Depositor	Identified by account and not by name	Depositor	Recommended	0..1	
DataCite	Coverage	Location (Geolocation)	The location(s) that the use of AI deals with	Location (Geolocation)	Recommended	0..n	Geonames
DataCite	Coverage	Data Time and Date	The start and end times that AI use deals with	Data Time and Date	Recommended	0..n	
DataCite	Coverage	Keywords	List of relevant keywords (free-text)	Keywords	Mandatory	1..n	
DataCite	Coverage	Keywords	AAID-Specific Keywords: Source of Model Training Data	Keywords	Mandatory	1..n	Source of Training Data

DataCite	Coverage	Keywords	AAID-Specific Keywords: Field of Application	Keywords	Mandatory	1..n	EuroSciVoc
DataCite	Coverage	Keywords	AAID-Specific Keywords: Type of Output	Keywords	Mandatory	1..n	Type of Output
DataCite	Relations	Related to	Other PIDs, publications, projects	Related to	Recommended	0..n	Relations Vocabulary
DataCite	Rights	Rightsholder	Name of the organisation or individual(s) owning the work (the output from AI use)	Rightsholder	Mandatory	1	RoR Registry, ORCID
DataCite	Rights	Licence	One of a number of specific licences, as applicable to the output fro AI use that is being referenced	Licence	Mandatory	1	Licence Registry
AIID	Model	Model.Title	Model title, as obtained from a registry		Mandatory	1	
AIID	Model	Model.relatedIdentifier	The PID defining the location where the model code can be obtained, or where more information about the model can be found if the code is not	relatedIdentifier	Mandatory	1	

			available.				
AIID	Model	Model.relatedIdentifierType	Select from a list of standardised types supported by the DataCite schema	relatedIdentifierType	Mandatory	1	DataCite relatedIdentifierType
AIID	Model	Model.relationType	Always, in this context, 'isDerivedFrom'	relationType	Mandatory	1	DataCite relationType
AIID	Model	Model.relatedMetadataScheme	Model metadata schema, for example CodeMeta	relatedMetadataScheme	Optional	0..1	
AIID	Model	Model.schemeURI	The URI to the schema definition	schemeURI	Optional	0..1	
AIID	Model	Model.schemeType	The type of schema, e.g.: XSD, DDT, Turtle	schemeType	Optional	0..1	
AIID	Model	Model.resourceTypeGeneral	Always, in this context, of type 'Software'	resourceTypeGeneral	Mandatory	1	DataCite resourceTypeGeneral
AIID	Training Data	Data.Title	A title for the training dataset, ideally as obtained from a repository		Mandatory	1	
AIID	Training Data	Data.relatedIdentifier	The PID defining the	relatedIdentifier	Mandatory	1	

			location where the training data can be obtained, or where more information about the model can be found if the code is not available.				
AIID	Training Data	Data.relatedIdentifierType	Select from a list of standardised types supported by the DataCite schema	relatedIdentifierType	Mandatory	1	DataCite relatedIdentifierType
AIID	Training Data	Data.relationType	Always, in this context, 'isDerivedFrom'	relationType	Mandatory	1	DataCite relationType
AIID	Training Data	Data.relatedMetadataScheme	Model metadata schema, for example CodeMeta	relatedMetadataScheme	Optional	0..1	
AIID	Training Data	Data.schemeURI	The URI to the schema definition	schemeURI	Optional	0..1	
AIID	Training Data	Data.schemeType	The type of schema, e.g.: XSD, DDT, Turtle	schemeType	Optional	0..1	
AIID	Training Data	Data.resourceTypeGeneral	Always, in this context, of type 'Software'	resourceTypeGeneral	Mandatory	1	DataCite resourceTypeGeneral

AIID	Performance	Data.Title	A title for the training dataset, ideally as obtained from a repository		Mandatory	1	
AIID	Training Data	Data.relatedIdentifier	The PID defining the location where the training data can be obtained, or where more information about the model can be found if the code is not available.	relatedIdentifier	Mandatory	1	
AIID	Training Data	Data.relatedIdentifierType	Select from a list of standardised types supported by the DataCite schema	relatedIdentifierType	Mandatory	1	
AIID	Training Data	Data.relationType	Always, in this context, 'isDerivedFrom'	relationType	Mandatory	1	
AIID	Performance	Performance	A value indicating performance assessment against a benchmark		Optional	1..n	
AIID	Performance	Performance.benchmark	A value from a list of benchmarking tests or methods		Optional	1..n	Benchmarks

A.3.2 JSON File Example

```
{  
  "model": {  
    "name": "GPT-4",  
    "version": "4.0",  
    "description": "A state-of-the-art generative language model developed by OpenAI, capable of  
generating coherent and contextually relevant text based on a given prompt.",  
    "developer": "OpenAI",  
    "licence": "OpenAI API License",  
    "release_date": "2023-03-15"  
  },  
  "training_data": {  
    "data_sources": [  
      {  
        "type": "web_crawl",  
        "description": "Diverse range of text from publicly accessible web pages."  
      },  
      {  
        "type": "books",  
        "description": "Digitised books covering various genres and topics."  
      },  
      {  
        "type": "academic_papers",  
        "description": "Research papers from multiple disciplines."  
      }  
    ]  
  }  
}
```

```
],
"data_size": "570 GB",
"data_preprocessing": "Text normalisation, deduplication, and filtering of sensitive information."
},
"capabilities": {
"languages_supported": ["English", "Spanish", "French", "German", "Chinese", "Japanese"],
"text_generation": true,
"summarisation": true,
"translation": true,
"question_answering": true,
"text_completion": true
},
"performance": {
"benchmark_scores": {
"BLEU": 35.7,
"ROUGE": {
"ROUGE-1": 44.3,
"ROUGE-2": 21.1,
"ROUGE-L": 41.7
}
}
},
"evaluation_datasets": [
"Common Crawl",
"SQuAD",
"GLUE"
]
```

```
},  
"usage_constraints": {  
  "restrictions": "Not to be used for generating harmful content, misinformation, or any application  
violating ethical guidelines.",  
  "recommended_usage": "Ideal for content creation, customer service automation, language  
translation, and educational tools."  
},  
"deployment": {  
  "runtime_environment": "Python 3.8+",  
  "dependencies": [  
    "transformers>=4.0.0",  
    "torch>=1.7.0"  
  ],  
  "API_endpoint": "https://api.openai.com/v1/engines/gpt-4/completions",  
  "example_usage": {  
    "input": "Explain the theory of relativity.",  
    "output": "The theory of relativity, developed by Albert Einstein, encompasses two interrelated  
theories: special relativity and general relativity..."  
  }  
},  
"contact_info": {  
  "support_email": "support@openai.com",  
  "documentation_url": "https://docs.openai.com/models/gpt-4"  
}  
}
```

Annexure B: Vocabulary

To be completed

B.1 Training Data Sources

#	Label	Description	URI	Reference
B.1-01	Web Crawl	Text data gathered from crawling publicly accessible web pages, including blogs, news sites, forums, and more.	sourceWebCrawl	
B.1-02	Books	Digitised texts from published books covering various genres and topics, including fiction, non-fiction, technical, and educational materials.	sourceBook	
B.1-03	Academic Papers	Scholarly articles and research papers from academic journals and conference proceedings across multiple disciplines.	sourceAcademicPaper	
B.1-04	News Articles	Articles from online news websites, including international, national, and local news sources.	sourceNewsArticle	
B.1-05	SocialMedia	Posts and comments from social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook, Reddit, and others, often used to capture conversational language and trends.	sourceNewsArticle	
B.1-06	Forums	Threads and posts from online discussion forums and communities, providing insights into niche topics and user interactions.	sourceForum	
B.1-07	Wikis	Articles from Wikipedia, Wikidata, and other sources, offering a broad range of structured and semi-structured information across	sourceWiki	

		various subjects.		
B.1-08	Government Publications	Official documents and publications from government agencies, including reports, statistics, regulations, and public records.	sourceGovernment	
B.1-09	Product Reviews	User-generated reviews from e-commerce platforms, offering opinions and feedback on a wide array of products and services.	sourceProductReview	
B.1-10	Patents	Documents from patent offices detailing inventions, including technical specifications and claims.		

B.2 Description of Capabilities

This vocabulary is a proposal at the current point in time.

Status: References are in process of being updated.

#	Label	Description	URI	Reference
B.2-01	Methods	Hypothesis generation, experiment design, and research process or workflow recommendations - these elements would typically be documented in a section on methods or as a formal methodology, and as such, any content contributed by AI needs to be cited and described in enough detail to be understood and scrutinised by third parties.	outputMethod	
B.2-01.01	Hypothesis Generation	Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly being integrated into research methodologies, for example in generating hypotheses.	outputHypothesis	[41] , [42]

B.2-02	Content Synthesis	Text mining results, synthesis of content from appraisal of available published materials, landscape analyses, literature reviews, and similar types of content in reports and publications: the source of the content needs to be citable, and wherever possible, provenance should be clear. Generative models are relatively effective at recognising semantic patterns, and as a result, imputing relations between concepts that were missed or overlooked by humans. Moreover, it is likely that AI will be well placed to enable cross-disciplinary research, which traditionally has been hampered by the necessary specialisation of researchers: AI can serve as a generalist in this context, able to translate concepts and approaches between disciplines.	outputContentSynthesis	
B.2-02.01	Text Generation	Ability to generate coherent and contextually relevant text based on a given prompt.	outputText	
B.2-02.02	Summary Synthesis	Ability to produce concise summaries of longer texts, capturing the main points and essential information.	outputTextSummary	
B.2-02.03	Question-Answer	Ability to provide accurate answers to questions based on the provided context or general knowledge.	outputAnswer	
B.2-02.04	Conversation	Ability to generate responses in a conversational context, enabling interactive dialogues with users.	outputConversation	
B.2-02.05	Creative Content	Ability to create narratives, images, audiovisual materials, and stories based on a given theme or prompt.	outputCreativeContent	
B.2-02.06	Text Completion	Ability to complete a given text prompt by generating the remaining text in a coherent manner.	outputTextCompletion	
B.2-02.07	Paraphrase	Ability to rephrase text while maintaining the original meaning.	outputParaphrase	
B.2-03	Coding and Algorithms	This application is not limited to research and development, and is one of the most effective ways in which generative AI is already being utilised in the community.	outputCodeAlgorithm	

B.2-03.01	Code Generation	Ability to generate programming code based on natural language descriptions or prompts.	outputCode	
B.2-04	Automation and Simulation	Includes automation of experiments, data collection and processing, and the simulation of processes, chemical and biological reactions, physical constructs, and both physical and virtual systems. It also includes automation of tasks involving a measure of human adjudication and consideration, for example by determining the level of sensitivity of a dataset.	outputAutomationSimulation	
B.2-05	Translation and Mapping	These closely related applications of AI all take a set of semantics and translate it to another, and some of these applications were the first widespread benefits from the application of AI to filter through to the general user community.	outputTranslationMapping	
B.2-05.01	Translation	Ability to translate text from one language to another while preserving meaning and context.	outputTranslate	
B.2-05.02	Query Processing	Ability to process and understand natural language queries to retrieve relevant information.	outputQuery	
B.2-05.03	Mapping	Ability to map one set of semantics to another, functionally similar to translation	outputMapping	
B.2-06	Patterns	Classification, Pattern and Entity Recognition		
B.2-06.01	Sentiment Analysis	Ability to analyse text and determine the sentiment expressed (e.g., positive, negative, neutral).	outputSentiment	
B.2-06.02	Transcription	Analysis of audiovisual material and creation of a text transcript of spoken phrases	outputTranscript	
B.2-06.03	Named Entity Recognition (NER)	Ability to identify and classify named entities (e.g., people, organisations, locations) within the text.	outputNamedEntity	
B.2-06.04	Classification	Ability to categorise text, images, audio, and video into predefined labels or classes based on its content.	outputClassification	

B.2-06.05	Object Recognition	A mechanism of classification that detect and potentially recognise objects in text, binary data, images, and audiovisual materials	outputObjectClassification	
B.2-06.06	Moderation	Ability to detect and filter inappropriate, harmful, or sensitive content in the text.	outputModeration	
B.2-06.07	Vectorisation	Ability to convert text into vector representations for use in various machine learning tasks, such as similarity search or clustering.	outputVector	
B.2-06.08	Recognition	Face, voice, and fingerprint recognition algorithms	outputRecognition	
B.2-06.09	Automated Diagnosis	Computer-aided diagnosis are systems that assist medical practitioners in the interpretation of medical images, audio recordings, or other audiovisual materials	outputDiagnosis	

B.3 Field of Application

This vocabulary is a proposal at the current point in time. Initially, it may be adequate to use a standardised vocabulary of scientific disciplines that is used widely in other contexts.

Proposal: [EuroSciVoc](#)

B.4 Benchmarks

This vocabulary is a proposal at the current point in time.

Status: References are in process of being updated.

#	Label	Description	URI	Reference
B.4-01	BLEU	BLEU is primarily used to assess the quality of machine-generated translations by comparing them to one or more human reference translations. It measures the overlap of n-grams (contiguous sequences of n words) between the generated text and the reference texts.	benchmarkBLEU	[43]

B.4-02	ROUGE	ROUGE is commonly used for evaluating automatic summarisation systems. It measures the overlap of n-grams, word sequences, and word pairs between the generated summary and reference summaries.	benchmarkROUGE	[44]
B.4-03	MLPerf	An industry-standard set of benchmarks for measuring the performance of machine learning software and hardware.	benchmarkMLPerf	[45]
B.4-04	MLMark	A benchmarking suite for evaluating the performance and power efficiency of embedded devices running machine learning workloads.	benchmarkMLMark	[46]
B.4-05	AI-Benchmark	A benchmarking tool designed for Android devices, it evaluates the performance of AI tasks on mobile devices, encompassing various real-world scenarios like image recognition, face parsing, and optical character recognition.	benchmarkAIBenchmark	[48]
...				

B.5 Risk Classification

Proposal based on EU framework legislation

#	Label	Description	URI	Reference
B.5-01	Low	No or minimal risk: these applications are permitted without obligations, and typically include trivial cases of assistance (completion, grammar checking, translations, searches, and coding examples)	riskLow	[3]
B.5-02	Medium	Transparency Obligations: Such applications are permitted but are subject to transparency obligations. The majority of research applications will fall in this category	riskMedium	[3]
B.5-03	High	High-risk applications: for example those that involve the adjudication of the subject or ranking against others or has significant implications if the result is incorrect (legally, in recruitment, medical diagnosis, etc.). Some	riskHigh	[3]

		specific obligations are involved here, for example ex-ante verification and conformity assessment. Research applications may fall into this category.		
B.05-04	Unacceptable	Not permitted: these applications carry unacceptable risk and will likely be prohibited or strongly regulated in most circumstances. An example used in the legislative framework is social scoring of individuals ⁹ .	riskUnacceptable	[3]

B.6 Additional Vocabularies

These are still being populated - to be completed in the next version

⁹ Interesting question arises here: Will research into these topics (e.g. using AI for social scoring) also be prohibited, or only its implementation?

Annexure C: Background Material

C.1 Landscape

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have been important R&D topics in computer science and digital sciences for some time, with ML making significant strides in terms of usability and general availability in the last decade. These advances have been largely focused on automated classification and application of advanced statistical methods to data, and finds expression in the quickly maturing field of Data Science and the [exponential growth of Data Scientist](#) as an occupation. (Note that not all Data Science methods are based on AI or ML).

ML is a sub-domain of AI, and for most of the past 50 years, this broader field has been slowly growing but tangible results were not common and widespread application was difficult and rare. Artificial intelligence is distinguished by the fact that it mimics or simulates human thought processes and is capable of dealing with fuzziness and ambiguity much more effectively than other methods. The well-publicised [Turing Test](#) requires that true AI cannot be distinguished as such by another human.

Deep Learning (DL) is especially important in the context of recent AI development - it provides techniques for training very large, multi-layers neural networks that have proven to be highly efficient at simulating human capabilities [\[29\]](#).

Most AI services are based on neural networks, and training and testing these networks - if it approached any size - was not really possible for most of the history of AI. Widening access to supercomputing platforms and [extraordinary growth in processing power](#) during the last 5-10 years changed the state of affairs radically, and the recent availability of AI platforms such as ChatGPT and

enhancements to image recognition and synthesis, translation, search, and coding services - to name a few - developed very rapidly and took most people by surprise.

C.1.1 Adoption Rate is Extraordinarily Quick

The adoption and use of AI platforms has been unlike any other technology wave before, with the use of the OpenAI platform (which includes ChatGPT variants) growing an order of magnitude quicker than any other major platform in history. OpenAI, within less than a year, has as many users and visits as reddit.com and NetFlix, and is gaining on TikTok [15].

Whether we want to know it or not, these figures suggest that a large number of employees - if not all of them - are already using AI platforms, either for work or personal applications. Interestingly, people from rich countries were traditionally less enthusiastic [16] about the use of AI, potentially because of concerns on unintended impacts. The EU has been relatively quick to develop a legislative framework for AI use [2], [3]. This also has implications - on the one hand, prudence is advisable, but on the other hand there is a significant possibility that loosely regulated use in emerging economies will result in very rapid gains in competitive advantage.

C.1.2 Adoption and Use is Outstripping Governance

One of the effects of the rapid adoption of AI has been that regulation and governance was not ready to deal with the phenomenon, and is struggling to keep up. As a precautionary measure, Italy initially banned the use of ChatGPT until further notice [19]. The EU has published a legislative framework [2],

[3] recently. In this respect, it leads the rest of the world, being the first major regulator to publish such legislation. The adoption process requires EU countries to adopt legislation based on the framework and it will mean that in practice, legislation may be some years away. IN the meantime, the provisions and general spirit of the legislative framework will assist with any interim policy or regulatory measures that one might consider.

The draft legislation is detailed and wide-ranging, and it will take a significant effort to review, analyse, and translate these into impacts on the organisation. One of the useful concepts associated with the legislation is a risk categorisation - something that one can use effectively in a policy response to AI [3].

C.1.3 Sophistication is Rapidly Increasing

The graphic illustrates how the latest version of the LLM engine that underpins OpenAI services - ChatGPT 4 - improved in a very short time on formal scores in common exams compared to its

predecessor [18]. This trend is likely to continue, and it is highly likely that near-perfect scores will be routine for all of the above within a short period of time. The poor performance in coding exams is interesting.

C.1.4 Citation, Provenance and Fraud

Provenance is a major concern. As illustrated below, [MidJourney](#) (similar to ChatGPT) can generate highly realistic images (or video) on the basis of a simple prompt [17], and one of the major technical challenges in future will be to determine whether a digital object or resource has been generated by AI, and if so, if the input provenance can be determined. Because of the nature of neural networks, where a large proportion of the training data potentially contributed via billions of probability-tuned parameters to a specific output, the concept of references as a mechanism for provenance breaks down. Hence some new thinking is required to deal with this aspect of AI [27].

Because provenance is not clear, there is no apparent way to establish trust in the output, and as a result, it is difficult to detect fraudulent objects or fake persona - which can easily be created ('Deep Fakes'). The possibilities for non-beneficial or criminal applications of AI, even with the platforms in its infancy, are therefore a major concern. This is recognised by the industry and some services have begun to provide a form of provenance [13], [14].

Provenance is tightly linked to citation, and it isn't clear at what point one can consider AI to be a knowledge-based synthesis that does not have to cite its sources, and when citation is necessary and appropriate. The human analogy is potentially useful here: an expert in any given field will be able to provide a significant synthesis on a topic without referral to sources, despite the knowledge being derived from those sources. On the other hand, any formal representation of that knowledge requires citation to comply with licence requirements and maintain the social contract in science and research, or both.

Moreover, since many of the GPT-type tools reuse prompts and resulting output as new learning materials - without necessarily distinguishing that the training material was generated artificially - the corpus of training material will become more and more artificial over time if left unchecked.

There is an additional concern that relates to influence in social networks, explored in detail in a report sponsored by OpenAI [\[10\]](#) - related to the expected reduction in cost and effort to generate content, create actors (persona), and dynamically personalise or tailor content to suit the consumer.

C.1.5 Alignment

An emerging field of study concerns so-called 'alignment' - developing mechanisms that serve as checks and balances for AI-based tools and services [\[25\]](#). The objectives, broadly speaking, are to ensure alignment with human objectives, that systems are safe and can be corrected, and that systems behave ethically [\[20\]](#).

C.1.6 Nuances and Indirect Impacts

The legislation developed by the EU [\[2\]](#) needs to be legally unambiguous, enforceable, and precise. It does not deal with indirect societal impacts as a result of the widespread use of AI, but this is, of course, a specific concern in the workplace and more generally in society. These concerns range from dilution of human skills and capacity due to reduced practice [\[22\]](#), to situations of job loss and redundancy due to AI.

A second class of nuance stems from systemic bias in models. Humans are generally able to distinguish these nuances and correct their synthesis from input materials, but large language models and generative tools based on them (such as ChatGPT) can not. Examples of three broad categories:

- Time bias: the training materials are overwhelmingly recent - humans have produced a lot of (digital) text in recent times - whether in formal research [\[23\]](#), fiction, non-fiction [\[24\]](#), or recreational - and as a result, AI will not be able to provide balanced views on concepts and rules that have changed over time - it will be biased towards more recent views.
- Regional and cultural bias: even after allowances for different languages, the bulk of training materials are based on western cultural perspectives, and that will show [\[21\]](#).
- Wealth bias: wealthier countries, corporations, and individuals contribute disproportionately to the training corpus for AI [\[21\]](#).

C.1.7 Accuracy

As generative models are used more and more, the deficiencies in respect of accuracy are also becoming clearer [\[10\]](#), [\[18\]](#), [\[38\]](#). There are well-documented examples of the type of synthesis that generative models are not capable of, and generally speaking, this is a result of an inability to distinguish three cases:

1. I can guess what the answer is but I do not have concrete facts to support it (imputing an answer);
2. The generative approach to answering a question is not appropriate, one needs to devise an algorithm or process to answer the question that involves logic, a heuristic, and/ or computation from data points;
3. The answer is based on the best information available but it fails a common sense check.

In future, generative models will become more sophisticated at selecting a course of action to arrive at a plausible answer, qualify the answer, and perform checks and balances (see alignment above). In the interim, and for some time to come, human verification of results - both in terms of process and content - will be required.

C.1.8 Cost and Spending Biasses

Finally: training of models and running them is expensive [\[4\]](#) - in fiscal and environmental terms. Spending and effort are also skewed towards generative AI-like implementations that have revenue potential, starving other important R&D topics in AI of funding, resources, and attention.

C.2 Detailed Inventory of AI Applications in Data Infrastructures

This detailed inventory of AI applications is intended as a starting point for a vocabulary of application of AI in the research data infrastructure context.

C.2.1 Systems Development

AI provides significant promise for improved systems development - especially in respect of code quality and speed of development. Since code is by definition tested, and needs to be reviewed and commented in a well-functioning development environment, the risks are relatively low in terms of provenance and trust.

One of the major practical challenges will be to benchmark current productivity and performance of development teams prior to the introduction of AI-assisted tools. It is problematic for two reasons: obtaining a measurement is difficult, and some development environments already include AI tools - resulting in a false benchmark. Benchmarking will be important if the tools involve a non-trivial cost, since such a cost will have to be justified through improved productivity and reduction in rework.

#	Consideration	Description	References
1	Coding Assistance	This is already well established and being used by many developers- e.g. via CoPilot .	[5]
2	Automated Code Generation	AI can be used to generate code automatically based on high-level specifications or natural language descriptions. This can help accelerate the development process and reduce manual coding efforts.	[5]
3	Code Quality and Bug Detection	AI techniques, such as static code analysis and machine learning algorithms, can assist in detecting bugs, vulnerabilities, and potential code quality issues. By analysing large codebases and patterns, AI can help developers identify and rectify potential problems early in the development cycle.	[5]
4	Optimisation	AI can optimise code by automatically identifying performance bottlenecks, suggesting improvements, and applying optimisations. This can lead to faster and more efficient code execution.	[5]
5	Testing	AI can help automate various aspects of software testing, including test case generation, test execution, and result analysis. AI-based testing frameworks can improve test coverage, detect anomalies, and identify edge cases that might be overlooked	[5]

		manually.	
6	Improved Context - NLP	NLP-powered AI systems can assist developers in understanding and extracting relevant information from documentation, research papers, and forums. This can aid in problem-solving, code reuse, and staying up to date with the latest advancements in the field.	[5]
7	Automated Deployment and Integration	Continuous Integration and Deployment (CI/CD): AI can facilitate automation and optimization in CI/CD pipelines. It can help with tasks like automated build and deployment, performance monitoring, and anomaly detection in production systems.	[5]
8	Simple Services	<p>As shown below, even a very generalised service such as ChatGPT can easily perform schematic transformations:</p> <p>In the XML representation, the JSON object has been converted to an XML structure. The top-level JSON object has become the root element <code><metadata></code>. The array within the JSON object is represented by an <code><item></code> element, which contains the individual key-value pairs as child elements.</p>	

How is the Open Source Community Leveraging OpenAI APIs?

Exploring +4000 starred GitHub Repositories

10

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#	Library/ Tool	Description	Environment	Reference
1	Tensorflow	A widely used open-source framework for machine learning and deep learning. It provides a comprehensive ecosystem for developing AI models.	Python Javascript	[20]
2	PyTorch	Open-source machine learning framework that emphasises flexibility and ease of use. It has extensive support for Python and enables building and training neural networks for various AI tasks.	Python	[20]

¹⁰ <https://i.redd.it/77pc9tcgrava1.png>

3	scikit-learn	A Python library that provides a range of machine learning algorithms and tools for data preprocessing, model selection, and evaluation. It is built on top of other Python libraries such as NumPy, SciPy, and matplotlib.	Python	[20]
4	Brain.js	A JavaScript library for neural networks that provides a high-level interface for creating and training various types of neural networks, including feedforward, recurrent, and convolutional networks.	Javascript	[20]
5	ml5.js	JavaScript library built on top of TensorFlow.js that simplifies the integration of machine learning models and pre-trained models into web applications. It provides pre-trained models for various tasks, including image classification and object detection.	Javascript	[20]
6	Deeplearning4j	An open-source deep learning framework for Java that integrates with other popular Java libraries such as Apache Spark and Hadoop. It provides support for developing and training deep neural networks.	Java	[20]
7	DL4J	Java-based deep learning library that focuses on scalability and distributed computing. It enables building and training deep neural networks on distributed systems.	Java	[20]
8	Weka	Open-source library for data mining and machine learning in Java. It provides a comprehensive set of tools and algorithms for tasks such as classification, clustering, and feature selection.	Java	[20]
9	PostGresML	Allows the embedding of AI and ML models directly in SQL queries.	Python	[20]

C.2.2 Content Authoring

#	Consideration	Description	References
1	Predictive Text and Autocorrection	This feature is ubiquitously present in authoring tools (Word, Google Docs, Programming Environments, Texting, etc.) and is largely beneficial and benign in the workplace - although there are concerns about its impact on younger people that are still learning writing skills.	[22]
2	Content Synthesis	Content synthesis is potentially the most contentious application of AI services in its current form: it is publicly documented that some content provided by services is false or inaccurate, and there is no way to verify provenance and attribute contributions. If applied with these concerns addressed, it is very useful and efficient. In such a scenario, skills erosion is also a concern.	[10], [13], [14], [17]
3	Translation	Machine language translation has been available for some time but the accuracy and availability of tools have significantly improved in the recent past. It is a low-risk, high efficiency application.	[34]
4	Research	Generative models can be used for summaries of topics and elements to consider within a topic, and this is a low-risk application if moderated afterwards by humans. Generative models are also commonly used to discover new ideas by reducing trial and error - especially for molecules.	[30]

C.2.3 Specific Services: Value-Addition

#	Consideration	Description	References
1	Speech Recognition	OpenAI provides a speech recognition service (Whisper) that 'approaches human accuracy' in respect of speech recognition. This is already being considered by the OH-SMART project for audio transcription.	[11]
2	Synthetic Data	Generative AI holds significant promise for synthetic data production and there are many tools emerging to assist with this.	[33]
3	Data Analysis	Data analysis can be a very complex task, especially in respect of	[35]

		complex or poorly structured data - AI improves efficiency of these processes.	
4	Data Transformation	Utilise machine learning algorithms to learn the mappings between dataset elements and standardised elements. This can involve training models on manually mapped instances or using unsupervised techniques to discover patterns and similarities.	[12]
5	Semantic Interoperability	There is significant potential for automation of data transformation specifically to improve semantic interoperability of legacy datasets - for example by looking for and matching standardised variables, recognising and implementing units of measure, applying dimensionality as applicable, etc.	[36]
6	Named Entity Recognition	Named Entity Recognition (NER) and entity linking approaches can be used to identify and link entities to relevant concepts.	[12]

C.2.4 Specific Services: Curation

#	Consideration	Description	References
1	Licence Selection	As far as can be determined, such attempts have not yet been made - but the possibility exists and the process will be straightforward if a large enough training data set can be found.	-
2	Anonymisation	There are at least 5 interrelated application options for use of AI in data anonymisation, ranging from the removal or masking of identifiable data to auditing.	[37]
3	Metadata Enhancement	AI techniques such as graph-based algorithms and reasoning can be employed to improve semantic connections, infer missing relationships, and enhance interoperability. NER will also be useful in this context (see above)	[12]
4	Completeness and QA	AI can assist with error and anomalous data detection, model development, and verification of completeness.	-

C.2.5 Specific Services: Search and Discovery

The web allows us to find anything and everything that has been indexed and matches the search pattern - but for most serious applications, these result sets are not precise enough and/ or too large to use meaningfully [4]. As a result, persistent identifiers and Linked Open Data has been developing as a solution to make such search results more precise, and coupled to metadata in repository catalogues, these have been the most sophisticated mechanisms available to us for providing high usability search and discovery systems.

Please list datasets in the DANS EASY repository dealing with the bronze age

I apologize for the confusion in my previous response. The DANS EASY repository is indeed a part of the Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) in the Netherlands. While I don't have direct access to the latest datasets, as of my knowledge cutoff in September 2021, here are a few examples of datasets related to the Bronze Age that were available in the DANS EASY repository:

1. "Bronze Age Landscapes: Tradition and Transformation in the Italian and Balkan Adriatic" - This dataset focuses on the Bronze Age landscapes of the Italian and Balkan Adriatic regions, including archaeological data, maps, and related documents.
2. "The Bronze Age on the Eastern Adriatic: Settlement Dynamics and Social Organization" - This dataset explores the Bronze Age settlements and social organization on the Eastern Adriatic coast, including excavation data, photographs, and reports.
3. "Bronze Age Pottery from the Southern Levant" - This dataset contains information on Bronze Age pottery from the Southern Levant region, including descriptions, photographs, and classification data.
4. "The Bronze Age Barrow Cemetery of Velim-Slonkovice (Czech Republic)" - This dataset focuses on the Bronze Age barrow cemetery of Velim-Slonkovice in the Czech Republic, including excavation reports, survey data, and associated materials.

Please note that these examples are based on the information available up to September 2021. It's recommended to visit the DANS EASY repository directly at <https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/> for the most up-to-date and comprehensive listing of datasets related to the Bronze Age.

It is conceptually at least possible to obtain better results from an open search result in the web by individually evaluating all results with a given context in mind - something that humans are good at - but which until now has been largely impractical because it will take too much time. AI opens up possibilities

for scaling the speed of such evaluation and its accuracy by many orders of magnitude, enhancing the role played by persistent identifiers and linked open data.

The example above, generated with ChatGPT (not necessarily the best service for the purpose, but illustrating a case in point) is interesting. It is clear that the AI service, provided that the dataset metadata formed part of its learning materials, will have no difficulty in finding relevant datasets. The only limitation is the scope of input material provided to the language model. Moreover, it is possible to fine-tune the model with specific training data [6] - something that potentially will be very useful in the repository context.

It will be an interesting additional experiment to test whether the AI service finds relevant datasets that meet the search criteria, but which were not explicitly indexed as such by DANS.

New enhancements to services can synthesise results in multiple steps by generating workflows automatically [26], and it is feasible already to construct an AI-based service that finds a list of matching records, and then transforms it into a specific output format requested by an end user.

Testing whether the language model is capable of providing the necessary LOD references to link Scientific Knowledge Graphs to its model failed for two test cases - ORCID IDs and re3data PIDs [8], [9]. Based on the replies one can gather that in general, personal data is not included in the language model, and that PIDs and similar identifiers were not considered for inclusion even if they were available.

Finally, it is inevitable that major search engines (Google, Bing, ...) will implement AI-based enhancements to their current platforms - as Bing has done already [14], and Google is attempting [14].

#	Consideration	Description	References
1	Enhancement	Semantic enhancement includes aspects of named entity recognition described earlier.	-
2	Summaries	" ... reviews results from across the web to find and summarise the answer you're looking for."	[13] , [14]
3	Fuzzy/ Semantic Search	Requires vectorised indexing of catalogue content and of natural language queries against the catalogue.	-
4	Search Refinement through Iteration	" ...empowers you to refine your search until you get the complete answer you are looking for by asking for more details, clarity and ideas – with links available so you can immediately act on your decisions."	[13]